

Synthesis and characterization of fluorescent CdSe quantum dots

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Abstract : Quantum dots (QDs) possess unique photochemical and photophysical properties that have wide applications in cellular imaging, tumor targeting, diagnostics and sensing devices. Thioglycolic acid (TGA) capped CdSe QDs with bright fluorescence and good monodispersity were synthesized. The growth kinetics of the nanoparticles was also studied. The nanoparticles possessed broad emission peaks corresponding band edge fluorescence and deep trap states. The CdSe quantum dots were characterized by Optical spectroscopy, Fluorescence spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier transform infra red (FTIR) spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy and Transmission electron microscopy (TEM). These CdSe QDs with broad band emission can have attractive roles in some biological tools like flow cytometric analysis and biolabelling.

Keywords : Nanostructures, optical materials, Debye-Scherrer powder method, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, luminescence.

Introduction

Quantum dots (QDs) have received significant attention in the past two decades due to their unique photochemical and photophysical properties. They have been used as fluorescent labels in cellular imaging, tumor targeting, diagnostics¹⁻⁶. Several improvements of the conventional aqueous synthetic method^{7,8} for thiol-capped CdTe nanocrystals (NCs) have been reported recently by different groups, ultrasonic⁹, microwave irradiation^{10,11}, hydrothermal synthesis^{12,13}, illumination¹⁴, organometallic method¹⁵⁻¹⁷, variation in the physical parameters like inert atmosphere¹⁸, variation of reagent concentrations^{13,19-21} and pH^{20,21} and use of thiol containing capping agent²².

In order to obtain crystalline, monodisperse nanoparticle, it is usually necessary to work at relatively high temperatures. This is where a solvent such as trioctyl phosphine oxide (TOPO) is useful for the preparation of semiconductor quantum dots^{20,21}, certain transition metal oxide nanoparticle⁹⁻¹⁷, and metal nanoparticle. In such examples, TOPO acts both as solvent and capping agent. The problem with these high-temperature solvents, apart from their toxicity, is that they can be very expensive, which makes scale up non-viable. Handling them (for example, attempting to distill/evaporate/purify) is also not

always easy. On the other hand, more common, inexpensive laboratory solvents also cause problems due to the limitations caused by their rather low boiling points. However, a simple method to circumvent this problem lies in using thiol containing capping agents like TGA with moderate boiling points (108 °C at 15 mm Hg for TGA). In this case the solvent is heated in a sealed vessel (autoclave, bomb, etc.), so that the autogenous pressure far exceeds the ambient pressure. This automatically raises the effective boiling point of the solvent.

The organometallic precursor method is the most popular route for the synthesis of high quality QDs. Recently, Yang *et al.* found a novel method to prepare CdSe nanocrystalline in aqueous solution with ultrasonic technique²³. Zhu *et al.* reported a new sonochemical method to synthesize hollow spherical CdSe nanocrystalline via an *in situ* template route²⁴. But the above methods are limited because of the insolubility in water and big size (more than 100 nm) of the as prepared CdSe nanocrystals. Although many other methods have also been developed for the preparation of CdSe in aqueous solution, wide size distribution limited their application in biology^{25,26}. In this paper, we summarize the recent activities of our groups aiming on further improvements of the aqueous

synthesis and the quality and luminescence properties of resulting thiol-capped CdSe quantum dots. In particular, our results correspond to the recently published findings^{13,19} that the use of an optimized molar ratio of Cd ions to thiol stabilizer indeed increases the room-temperature photoluminescence quantum efficiency of TGA-capped CdTe NCs. Furthermore several advantages of TGA as the capping agent in the aqueous synthesis of CdSe NCs provides an expansion of the range of available particle sizes, the possibility of shifting the emission wavelength further to the infrared and an extended exciton decay. The last phenomenon is explained by considering the energetic of the traps associated with surface Se atoms with respect to the valence-band position of the CdSe NCs. In this paper, a simple method has been described to synthesize water dispersible CdSe QDs by organometallic route with small size (1–3 nm). The precursors, CdCl₂·H₂O and Na₂SeO₃ were reacted together with thioglycolic acid (TGA) as stabilizing agent. The result showed that the product was well formed when the initial molar ratio of Cd/Se was 1 : 0.40, which have been characterized by absorption spectra, photoluminescence spectra, X-ray diffractometer, UV-Visible spectroscopy, IR spectroscopy and Raman spectroscopy.

Experimental

Synthesis :

In a typical synthesis, 12.0 mM CdCl₂·H₂O was dissolved in to nitrogen saturated 100 ml de-ionized water in 250 ml 3-neck round-bottom flask. Then 30.0 mM TGA was added under stirring. The protocol has been described in Scheme 1. The molar ratio of Cd²⁺ : TGA : Se²⁻ was fixed at 12 : 3 : 30. The pH was adjusted to 9 with 1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH solution. After that, this solution was injected to the 3-neck round-bottom and heated at 120 °C for 10 min. Subsequently 3.0 mM Na₂SeO₃ was added under vigorous stirring at N₂ atmosphere for 4 h. After cooling to room temperature, the resulting products were precipitated by methanol and superfluous TGA, Na₂SeO₃ and Cd²⁺ in the resulting products were removed with centrifugation at 7000 rpm for 15 min. The resultant precipitate was re-dispersed in water and re-precipitated by methanol for more than 3 times. The investigation was carried out in duplicate to confirm reproducibility of the experimental results.

Based on the above results and some literatures, a possible mechanism for the formation of CdSe QDs is suggested as follows.

Firstly, when the TGA was added to CdCl₂ solution, a white colloid was produced immediately that indicated

Scheme 1. Schematic presentation of the synthesis of thioglycolic acid-capped CdSe quantum dots. First stage : formation of CdSe precursors by introducing Na₂SeO₃ to the CdCl₂·H₂O. Second stage : formation and growth of CdSe nanocrystals promoted by reflux.

that Cd^{2+} formed complex with TGA as shown in eq. (1).

When the Na_2SeO_3 solution was injected to the 3-neck round-bottom flask at 120°C the SeO_3^{2-} can be reduced to Se^{2-} (eq. (2)) that immediately reacted with the $\text{Cd}(\text{TGA})^{2+}$ compounds (eq. (3)), resulting in the formation of CdSe nuclei. With the CdSe nuclei growing gradually, the CdSe QDs were formed at last (eq. (4)).

In the basic condition, the $\text{Cd}(\text{TGA})^{2+}$ compound reacted quickly with SeO_3^{2-} (eq. (3)), resulting in the formation of CdSe nuclei. With the CdSe nuclei growing gradually, the CdSe QDs were formed at last (eq. (4)).

Characterization of CdSe core QDs :

UV/Visible absorption were recorded using the Varian Cary 300 UV-Vis spectrophotometer with samples placed in quartz cuvettes (1-cm path length). The optical measurements were carried out using water as the reference. Photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy was gathered on a Perkin-Elmer LS 50B (Xenon flash lamp) with an excitation wavelength of 450 nm and a 1% attenuator. QDs in ethanol were placed in an open sided 1 cm path length quartz cuvette for both UV-Vis absorption and PL measurements. The IR measurement was carried out on Hewlett-Packard with samples placed in silica cuvettes (1-cm path length). Crystal structure was determined using an X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique. XRD patterns were recorded using a Siemens D-500 diffractometer X-ray diffractometer with nickel filtered CuK_α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$). Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) image was obtained on a Philips CM-300 microscope operating at 300 kV. Samples for TEM studies were prepared by dropping diluted solutions of CdSe QDs onto 400-mesh carboncoated copper grids with the solvent evaporated immediately in vacuum.

Results

Fig. 1 shows typical TEM image of TGA-capped CdSe QDs with sizes $3.28 \pm 0.07 \text{ nm}$. XRD measurements (Fig. 2) show that in the described synthetic protocol

Fig. 1. TEM image of TGA-capped CdSe QDs as $3.28 \pm 0.07 \text{ nm}$ average size, with a PL maximum at 450 nm.

Fig. 2. X-Ray powder diffraction pattern of CdSe QDs prepared at 120°C .

CdSe seems to crystallize in a cubic close packed (zinc blende) structure. The characteristic zinc blende planes of 111, 220, and 311 located at 25.42° , 43.05° , and 50.96° in the 2θ range of 20° – 70° for CdSe were observed. However, estimated from the relative intensity in the XRD patterns, the wurtzite CdSe nanocrystals are not dominant (less than 10%). Presumably, the formation of cubic phase of CdSe in our synthetic procedure is attributed to the moderate temperature of synthesis (120°C). It is generally accepted that CdSe crystallizes predominantly in cubic phase when the annealing temperature is below 200°C , and the hexagonal phase becomes dominant when the annealing temperature is higher than 300°C ²⁷⁻³⁰. However, in some cases at low temperature of synthesis, the observed X-ray diffraction patterns can

be explained also by the presence of zinc blende stacking faults along the (002) direction that is very typical for wurtzite II-VI nanocrystals^{29,31}.

The size was calculated from XRD results estimated from the widths of the major diffraction peaks observed in Fig. 1 through the Scherrer's formula eq. (5),

$$D_{hkl} = \frac{k\lambda}{\Delta_{hkl} \cos \theta} \quad (5)$$

where D_{hkl} is the linear dimension of the coherent diffracting domain along a direction normal to the diffraction plane (hkl), λ is X-ray wavelength in angstroms (1.5418 Å in our case), k is a crystal shape constant (0.9), θ is the angle of reflection of the peak, and Δ_{hkl} is the corrected full width at half-maximum (fwhm) of the peak in radians, which was calculated as the square root of the difference between the squares of the sample's and the reference's fwhm. The dimensions of the CdSe QDs calculated from the widths of the XRD is depicted in Fig. 2. The size of the CdSe QDs was calculated from XRD according to eq. (5) and average CdSe QDs was found as 3.28 ± 0.07 nm in diameter. The high size homogeneity was also reflected from the sharp absorbance spectra of CdSe QDs dispersed in aqueous solution (Fig. 3).

The temporal evolution of absorption spectra of the CdSe QDs was shown in Fig. 3. The reaction time was counted after the injection of the Na_2SeO_3 solution into the $\text{Cd}(\text{TGA})^{2+}$. The reaction was monitored by recording the absorption spectra of the aliquots taken periodically from the reaction vessel. When the reaction time was 0 min, the excitonic absorption peak was not detected (not shown in Fig. 3). After 60, 180 and 240 min, all of the positions of the excitonic absorption peaks are at about 443, 452 and 456 nm respectively. It indicated the morphological growth of CdSe QDs. The sharp absorption spectra with clear excitonic features indicated a narrow size distribution of the CdSe QDs. In the absorbance spectra (Fig. 3), a small hump at ~ 540 nm was detected that is attributed to the formation of an exciton corresponding to HOMO-LUMO transition (first exciton). The absorption peak of water soluble QDs was slightly red shifted. The photoluminescence spectrums of the synthesized CdSe QDs were recorded at 450 nm with broad peaks at 472 nm and 481 nm at 60 min and 180 min (Fig. 4), respectively. Obviously, this broad and bright fluorescence is not from a large size distribution, and there-

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra of CdSe QDs synthesized at 120 °C.

Fig. 4(a). Fluorescence spectrum of TGA-capped CdSe QDs synthesized at 120 °C. The PL spectrum was recorded at $\lambda_{\text{excitation}} = 450$ nm.

Fig. 4(b). Fluorescence spectrum of TGA-capped CdSe QDs synthesized at 120 °C. The PL spectrum was recorded at $\lambda_{\text{emission}} = 450$ nm.

fore, it probably is from trap states to explain the possible reason for this bright broad fluorescence. The PL spectrum of TGA-capped CdSe QDs synthesized at 120 °C consisted of two parts : a shoulder that probably corresponds to band edge fluorescence and the other part that corresponds to deep trap fluorescence as a result of surface defects (this fluorescence is broad and with high intensity) (Figs. 4(a) and 4(b))^{32,33}. The relatively sharp exciton peak in the absorbance spectra indicates that the synthesized QDs are size and shape monodisperse. Furthermore, the optical properties are good, with band edge PL and narrow peak widths.

Usually, the broad fluorescence spectrum of CdSe QDs is considered as a shortcoming. However, in these contexts of their small, homogeneous size, with reasonably simple and highly reproducible synthetic protocol, we consider these QDs attractive for biolabeling, and application in bioimaging experiments. Because of their small size and high quantum yield³⁴, it is possible to conjugate several QD particles on one macromolecule (e.g. protein, DNA, etc.) and thus to increase significantly the fluorescence intensity, giving a possibility for highly sensitive analyses (even for detection of single molecules).

Fig. 3 shows the UV-Vis adsorption spectra obtained from an aqueous solution. The CdSe has characteristic exciton adsorption peaks at 443, 452 and 456 nm at 60, 180, 240 min respectively. As reaction proceeds the adsorption peak from the quantum dots adsorption peak red shifted slightly and broadened and similar trend was also noted in PLs (Fig. 4). The red shifts in the absorption spectra of the CdSe QDs in relation to the parent material are attributed to relaxation of quantum confinement resulting from the growth of the shell³⁵. The broadening of the second absorption band in 452 nm is also due to surface passivation by the CdSe, as the second excited state has more electron density close to the particle surface so that its energy should be more sensitive to surface derivatization³⁶.

The emission spectrum of CdSe is broad, indicating a wide size distribution, as confirmed by the shape of the absorption spectrum. This observation is probably due to Ostwald ripening. Fig. 5 presents the FTIR spectra of CdSe QDs. The characteristic peaks are located at 1377 and 1591 cm^{-1} , and are attributed to the symmetric ring breathing and the C-C and -COOH stretching modes, respectively. Acidic group is a good electron donor due to the presence of a pair of isolated oxygen electrons that is delocalized over its entire aromatic ring. CdSe quan-

Fig. 5. FTIR spectra of CdSe QDs.

um dots show a good electron affinity, meaning that the nitrogen readily coordinates with them to form a stable complex. Therefore, it is concluded that the good interactions of the TGA with the CdSe surface, due to hydrogen bonding indicates the formation of CdSe quantum dots. In other words the complex ions with selenium form a chain structure of metastable molecular building blocks. By increasing temperature to 120 °C the latter decomposes, giving CdSe QDs. It is worth mentioning that, the intermediate is stable at low temperature and at higher temperature it decomposes, giving CdSe QDs.

Fig. 6 shows the Raman spectrum of the CdSe QDs taken using a 632 nm excitation laser. A well-resolved vibrational band at 210 cm^{-1} is observed in Fig. 6. The peak observed at 210 cm^{-1} is reported to be due to the

Fig. 6. Raman spectra of the CdSe QDs taken using a 632 nm excitation laser.

first lattice optical mode (1LO) of bulk CdSe³⁷, indicating that it should be due to the lattice vibration of CdSe nanoparticles. The weak and poorly resolved Raman peak at around 430 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the first overtone of the 209 cm⁻¹ band (2LO), and this provides further evidence for CdSe formation. Raman measurements on hybrids containing CdSe nanoparticles of different size showed no detectable frequency shifts for the range of sizes achieved in this work. The characteristic Raman peaks of CdSe were found at 210, 430, 495 and 708 cm⁻¹, which correspond to the CdSe longitudinal optical (LO) phonons and its overtone²⁰.

Conclusion :

A simple synthetic technique has been followed to obtain stable, size-tuned CdSe QDs in water using TGA as capping agent. A water dispersible, small size CdSe QDs have been successfully synthesized via an organo-metallic method. The CdSe QDs possessing size homogeneity with a broad fluorescent spectrum. These QDs can be easily dispersed in aqueous solutions with enhancement of their quantum yield and preservation of their photostability. The broad fluorescent QDs are appropriate for application in flow cytometric and western blot analyses. The UV-Vis absorption study revealed a fast growth process in the formation of high quality CdSe QDs. The phases of the as-synthesized CdSe QDs were zinc blende (cubic), not wurtzite (hexagonal). By the suitable choice of source and synthetic parameters, it is reasonable to expect that the present study could be extended to other green and low cost routes for large-scale synthesis of high-quality QDs.

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